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Data management plan (DMP)

Evaluation of a simple score- based Natural Language Processing (NLP) algorithm

EOSCSecretariat.eu

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1.0	14/05/2023	First version of DMP – created for start of project

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20%E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

The following tables contain the produced and reused datasets.

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	[20230513]_merged_preprocessed.csv	Structured text	CSV	30 MB	no
P2	Evaluation pipeline	Source code	Jupyter Notebook	50 MB	no
P3	[20230513]_rating_confusion.svg	Images	SVG	50 KB	no
P4	[20230513]_category_confusion.svg	Images	SVG	50 KB	no
P5	[20230513]_predicted_rating.csv	Structured text	CSV	25 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Amazon Customer Review Data	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3549704	CC BY 4.0	no
R2	Google Play Store Data	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2844022	CC BY 4.0	no
R3	NRC Word-Emotion Association Lexicon	http://saifmohammad.com/WebPages/NRC-Emotion-Lexicon.htm	Free usage, no redistribution	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Our data pipeline will consist of three steps. Each step is implemented using a Python script.

(1) We will merge dataset R1 (Amazon Customer Review Data) and dataset R2 (Google Play Store Data) and filter the stopwords that are included in the reviews (such as “this”, “and”, “or”) using the “nltk” package. This generates dataset P1.

(2) We will process the review text and calculate, based on this text, a rating for the review. For this, we will use dataset P1 as input. We will then use dataset R3 (NRC Word-Emotion Association Lexicon), which is a dataset that maps words to either being positive or negative, to calculate the predicted rating of the review using the simple NLP algorithm. In specific, we will increase the rating of a review for each positive word found and decrease it for each negative word found. These findings will then be stored as P5.

(3) Based on the real rating of the review and the predicted rating of the review, we will output two confusion matrices P3 (“[yyymmdd]_rating_confusion.pdf”) and P4 (“[yyymmdd]_category_confusion.pdf”). The former will describe how well the NLP algorithm can predict the rating of a review (1=bad review, 5=good review), while the latter will describe how well it can categorize the review in “good review” and “bad review”.

We will reuse the existing datasets R2 (Google Play Store Data) and R1 (Amazon Customer Review Data) to use it as the input reviews for the evaluation. Furthermore, we will reuse the dataset R3 (NRC Word-Emotion Association Lexicon) that categorize words as either positive or negative to calculate the predicted rating of the review.

There are no constraints on re-use of existing data. R3 (NRC Word-Emotion Association Lexicon), however, may not be redistributed, thus it will not be included in the repository that we provide. Persons interested in replicating the pipeline will thus be required to download the dataset from the given source.

We will use CSV-Files for storing the results of the evaluation, since this is the widespread data format in the NLP community, and it is easy to parse. Moreover, we opted to make the confusion matrices available as SVG-Files, since they allow lossless presentation of the visualization compared to other image formats such as PNG or JPG.

To document data provenance for our dataset, we will use metadata standards and documentation best practices. First, we will document the sources of our data. We will also document the cleaning and preprocessing steps applied to our data, including any data transformations or filtering. This will include information about the software tools used and any assumptions made during the cleaning process. Second, we will document the analysis techniques used to analyze our data, including any software packages or libraries used, the version numbers used in the analysis. This will include information about the data visualization and plots created from our data, including the software tools and the settings used to create the visualizations. To organize and structure this information, we will use the metadata standard DataCite, as well as documentation practices such as README files and code comments. We will also use version control tools such as Git to track changes to our data over time, and to create a clear audit trail of the data's lineage.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

Data organization

The evaluation pipeline will be organized as follows: The project’s root folder will contain three folders: “code”, “data” and “documentation”. The “code” folder will contain the Jupyter notebook files, the “data” folder the input and output datasets and the “documentation” folder metadata for the evaluation pipeline and the architecture.

The filenames of the output files will follow the following convention and will include a timestamp of creation: “[yyyymmdd]_[filename].[extension]”.

Jupyter Notebook files will follow the following convention: “[sequence_number]_[description_of_script].ipynb”. The sequence number describes the order in which the scripts need to be executed.

Metadata and Documentation

The data will be treated according to the following criteria:

- (F) We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata (see section 5).
- (A) We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- (I) We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas, and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- (R) We will make our data reusable by adding metadata to all published data sets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. Licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Version control for the evaluation pipeline is automated using Git.

We will use DataCite as the metadata standard to describe the produced data. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data. We will create a metadata file for every file produced in the experiment, as well as for the evaluation pipeline itself. These metadata files include information about the document they are referencing (using the document’s DOI), their title, data types, production date, keyword, license etc. In case of CSV files, they will also include a description of the meaning of each column.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

We will provide extensive documentation on how to validate the data analysis and facilitate data reuse by describing the process in detail in the project's README file. We also provide intermediary results and annotate the source code with comments in order to enhance reproducibility.

All produced outputs, including the analysis pipeline, will be assigned a unique identifier.

2b Data quality control

Data quality checks will be done, e.g., logical errors in the data, data curation, and version control. Furthermore, the experiment pipeline and the data will be peer-reviewed.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

P1 ([20230513]_merged_preprocessed.csv), P3 ([20230513]_rating_confusion.pdf), P4 ([20230513]_category_confusion.pdf), P5 ([20230513]_predicted_rating.csv), R1 (Amazon Customer Review Data), R2 (Google Play Store Data), R3 (NRC Word-Emotion Association Lexicon) will be stored in TUownCloud: TUownCloud is a sync&share service provided by TU.it for TU Wien members. It runs on TU.it servers and offers features known from public cloud systems such as Dropbox, for

example, the exchange of data with authorized persons. Deleted files can be recovered within 180 days. These files will be backed up once a day.

P2 (Evaluation pipeline) will be stored in GitHub. External storage will be used due to possible collaboration with researchers from other institutions. These files will be backed up at least once a day.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	no access
P2	writing	writing	no access
P3	writing	writing	no access
P4	writing	writing	no access
P5	writing	writing	no access
R1	reading only	reading only	no access
R2	reading only	reading only	no access
R3	reading only	reading only	no access

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

The project produces no sensitive data.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

The output datasets will be licenses under the CC0 licence. The evaluation pipeline will be MIT-licensed.

Two of three input datasets (R1, R2) will be included in the evaluation pipeline. Legal restrictions on R3, however, prevent the distribution of the dataset. Interested people will have to download the dataset from the publisher's website.

Saif M. Mohammad has the rights to dataset R3 (NRC Word-Emotion Association Lexicon) and controls its access.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2023-05-14	Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933975	CC0 1.0
P2	Open		2023-05-14	GitHub	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933965	MIT
P3	Open		2023-05-14	Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933985	CC0 1.0
P4	Open		2023-05-14	Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7903932	CC0 1.0
P5	Open		2023-03-14	Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7933985	CC0 1.0

The repositories used in this project are described in the following paragraph:

ZENODO builds and operates a simple and innovative service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. ZENODO enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to easily share the long tail of small research results in a wide variety of formats including text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and images across all fields of science. display their research results and get credited by making the research results citable and integrate them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission. easily access and reuse shared research results.
<https://zenodo.org/>

Output and input datasets: Potential users do not need specific tools to access the data. They, however, need software that is capable of opening CSV files (a simple text editor suffices), as well as PDF files.

Evaluation pipeline: Potential users are required to either be able to run Docker (<https://docker.com>) or run Python code on their machine. We provide information on how to run the experiment in the project's README.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

Data will be stored for at least ten years in accordance with the RDM Policy of the TU Wien, as summarized in the table below.

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	Zenodo	10 years	Members of the scientific community
P2	GitHub	10 years	
P3	Zenodo	10 years	
P4	Zenodo	10 years	
P5	Zenodo	10 years	
R3	TUownCloud	10 years	Users interested in reproducing the experiment (only in case the original dataset is not accessible anymore)

Because we are not allowed to distribute R3 (NRC Word-Emotion Association Lexicon) and include it in the evaluation pipeline, we preserve it in case the original dataset is taken offline.

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The data officer will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The lead country researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0